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Pastoral Counselling and Trauma-Responsive Healing for Managing Victims of Terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the pivotal role of pastoral counseling in facilitating trauma resolution and fostering healing within Nigerian communities, particularly in the northeastern region profoundly impacted by terrorism. Employing a mixed-methods research design, questionnaires were distributed to 200 representative individuals, and in-depth interviews were conducted with pastoral caregivers and community leaders, selected through stratified random sampling. With 93% of the respondents responding with a no to existing resources/initiatives, 7 % agreed that there existed few resources and initiatives from NGOs in their affected localities. The research highlights the dearth of initiatives and resources for trauma-responsive healing in affected communities, with 93% of respondents indicating a lack thereof. Findings also reveal varying perceptions regarding the effectiveness of pastoral counseling, with only 44% strongly agreeing with its efficacy, while 53.5% expressed moderate agreement. The questionnaire utilized in the study was self-structured and underwent rigorous psychometric evaluation, including assessments of reliability and validity. In light of these findings, the study emphasizes the critical need for trauma-informed interventions administered by pastoral caregivers, informed by the Traumatic Growth Theory, to address the multifaceted challenges faced by Nigerian communities post-terrorism. This paper underscores the potency of pastoral counseling as an indispensable tool in nurturing the healing process and fostering resilience amidst adversity.

Keywords: Healing, Pastoral Counseling, Trauma, Terrorism and Trauma-responsive

Introduction

Over a prolonged duration, Nigerian communities, with a specific focus on the northeastern region, have grappled with the formidable challenge of terrorism. The principal perpetrator of these attacks has been the extremist organization known as Boko Haram, which espouses the ideology that "Western Education is forbidden." The terrorism problem in Nigerian communities has had far-reaching consequences, including loss of life, displacement, economic disruption, and a climate of fear, insecurity, and traumatic experiences. Corroborating this, Onuoha (2014) records that "since July 2009 when Boko Haram engaged Nigerian forces in a short-lived anti-government uprising, the group has grown to become a serious national, regional, and international concern". From the bombing of the United Nations Building in Abuja, which resulted in the tragic loss of 23 lives, to the infamous kidnapping of more than 200 schoolgirls in 2014, an event that sparked the global campaign known as Bring Back Our Girls, the impact of

these actions by Boko Haram has instilled deep-seated fear and trauma within the Nigerian nation.

In the face of adversity, human resilience often emerges, guiding the path towards healing and restoration. However, for Nigerian communities deeply affected by the venomous grip of terrorism, the wounds inflicted extend far beyond the physical realm, reaching into the depths of the human psyche. The psychological and emotional traumas wrought by acts of violence, loss, and displacement have left indelible imprints on individuals, families, and entire communities. In these troubled times, the role of pastoral counseling emerges as a beacon of hope, offering solace and support to those grappling with the aftermath of terrorism.

Grounded in the principles of spirituality, compassion, and cultural understanding, pastoral counseling possesses the potential to address the unique psychological and emotional needs of individuals affected by terrorism. Drawing upon Traumatic Growth Theory, developed by Richard Tedeschi and Lawrence Calhoun, we can understand how trauma can lead to positive psychological changes and personal growth. This theory suggests that traumatic events like terrorism can cause vulnerability and distress, prompting the need for pastoral counseling to help individuals build resilience, facilitate meaning, and foster spiritual growth (Bassel, 2015).

Relating this theory to the Nigerian context, it becomes evident that traumatic events such as terrorism often leave individuals and communities in a state of vulnerability and distress. It is in such states that pastoral counseling emerges to assist individuals in building resilience, finding meaning in the aftermath of trauma, and fostering spiritual growth.

This study seeks to explore the frontiers of pastoral counseling in the Nigerian context, particularly in the northeastern regions deeply scarred by terrorism. The paper aims to examine the unique challenges faced by pastoral counselors working in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism, delving into the delicate balance required between providing spiritual guidance and psychological support for the victims.

Trauma and its State among Nigerian Communities in Related Literatures

Trauma is an emotional, psychological, or physical response to shocking, distressing, or harmful events, which can significantly impact an individual's mental health. In line with this school of thought, Bessel in his book "The Body Keeps the Score" explores how trauma impacts the body and offers insights into various therapeutic approaches. The author opined that individuals can get through the difficulties that arise from their traumatic experience through participation in his therapeutic approaches (Bassel, 2015). Herman in her work "Trauma and Recovery" discusses the long-term effects of trauma and the process of recovery, emphasizing the importance of validation. She explained the concept of trauma as the process of recovery and emphasized the need for empowerment and validation in the recovery process (Herman, 1992). Correlating Bassel's opinion, Friedman (2000) also in his work "Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder" delved into the clinical aspects of PTSD, including its diagnosis and treatment. The scholar did well by highlighting some of the experiences such as rape, sexual abuse, and domestic violence as possible causes of trauma. In the same vein, Goodman and Espstein (2007) in their work "The Impact of Trauma on Communities" examined on a broader scale how trauma affects communities as a whole, including social and cultural aspects.

On the effects of Trauma on individuals and communities, scholars have acknowledged the profound impact of trauma on mental health often leading to conditions like anxiety and depression. Chronic health issues and heightened stress responses have been noted as consequences of trauma. Friedman (2000) opines that sometimes trauma can destabilize communities, leading to crime, substance abuse, and a breakdown of social structures. However, there have been other opinions from recent scholars that trauma destabilizes relationships and social functioning, contributing to feelings of isolation.

On the state of Trauma Counseling in Nigerian Communities, scholars such as Haldun & Opeyemi (2016) and Abdul (2017) noted that scarcity of mental health resources has been a major challenge in Nigerian communities. These scholars also stressed the importance of culturally sensitive approaches to trauma counseling in Nigeria, incorporating traditional healing practices. Sheikh, et al. (2014) highlighted community-based organizations and NGOs as vital in providing trauma support where formal services are lacking. As of 2021, there were nascent efforts by the Nigerian government to improve mental health services, but challenges persisted.

It must, however, be taken into consideration that the literature on trauma and pastoral counseling approaches is limited, particularly in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism. While scholars have identified trauma as a challenging phenomenon, there is a lack of comprehensive research on the specific needs and experiences of individuals in these communities, making it crucial to address this gap.

Understanding Trauma and its Challenge in Nigerian Context

Trauma is a deeply distressing experience that can have long-lasting psychological and emotional effects on individuals. Understanding trauma in the Nigerian context involves considering the cultural, religious, and spiritual dimensions that influence how individuals experience and cope with traumatic events. In Nigeria, religion plays a significant role in people's lives, and it often shapes their understanding of trauma and healing processes.

Trauma counseling in Nigeria encounters obstacles due to scarce resources, cultural beliefs, and social stigma. Traditional values and cultural norms frequently shape the perception of trauma, resulting in a shortage of trained trauma counselors and insufficient facilities. This stigma deters individuals from seeking treatment, while a lack of awareness about the benefits of trauma counseling impedes early intervention. Religious beliefs, including prayer, meditation, and attending religious services, offer a framework for comprehending traumatic events and providing coping strategies. The religious and spiritual dimensions of trauma in Nigeria are influenced by individual beliefs, cultural practices, and affiliations, making it crucial to consider this diversity.

Nigerian Christianity tackles trauma by incorporating its distinct religious beliefs and practices. Traumatic experiences, such as violence, loss, or natural disasters, impact individuals irrespective of their religious affiliation. To combat this crisis, Nigerian Christians employ spiritual activities like prayer, fasting, and seeking counsel from religious authorities. The supportive nature of the Christian community contributes to the process of healing.

Hence, understanding trauma in the Nigerian Christian context requires acknowledging the religious and spiritual dimensions that influence the healing process. By recognizing the specific

beliefs and practices of Nigerian Christianity, individuals can find solace, hope, and meaning in their traumatic experiences. Religious leaders and mental health professionals need to work collaboratively in providing support and guidance to those affected by trauma within this context.

Methodology/Data Collection on Advancing Pastoral Counseling Approaches for Trauma-Responsive Healing in Northeastern Nigerian Communities Affected by Terrorism

Employing a mixed-methods research design, this study investigates Pastoral Counselling and Trauma-Responsive Healing for Managing Victims of Terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria. Quantitatively, 200 individuals affected by terrorism were surveyed using the "Pastoral Counselling and Trauma-Responsive Healing Assessment Questionnaire," employing a random sampling technique to ensure diversity. Concurrently, qualitative insights were garnered through in-depth interviews with pastoral caregivers and community leaders, selected via a stratified random sampling method to represent various affected demographics and regions.

Data analysis involved quantitative assessment through percentages and statistical methods to discern trends, while qualitative data from interviews was thematically analyzed to identify recurring patterns and perspectives. This mixed-methods approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in addressing trauma among victims of terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria, offering valuable insights for the development of effective interventions and support programs.

Data Analysis

Chart I

Section: Demographic Information Gender
200 responses

The chart 1 above represents the demographic information showing that females responded more to the questionnaire than the male gender.

Chart II

Occupation
200 responses

Chart II represents the occupation of the participants.

Chart III

Age
200 responses

Chart III shows the age categories of the respondents indicating that majority of the respondents were between the youthful ages of 18-25

Chart IV

Have you or someone you know experienced trauma as a result of terrorism?
200 responses

Findings showed that 11.5% of the total respondents never experienced trauma as a result of terrorism in the study location. However, 88.5% of the total respondents agreed that they knew someone and may have experienced trauma as result of terrorism.

Chart V

Are you familiar with pastoral counseling approaches for trauma responsive healing?
200 responses

Chart V revealed that 51% of the respondents in the study locale were somewhat familiar with pastoral counseling approaches; 15.5% were not familiar with the approaches at all; 33.5% claimed to be familiar with the approaches in pastoral counseling regarding the subject matter. The level of awareness according to the findings seems very low and needs to be addressed.

Chart VI

How effective do you think pastoral counseling approaches are in promoting trauma responsive healing in affected communities?
200 responses

The findings from this chart shows that majority of the respondents were not really certain with the effectiveness of pastoral counseling approaches in promoting trauma responsive healing in affected communities. With only 44% agreeing to pastoral counseling approaches as very effective in trauma responsive healing, 53.5% agreed to a moderate level thereby leaving 2.5 % disagreeing totally.

Chart VII

Which of the following pastoral counseling approaches do you think would be most beneficial for trauma responsive healing in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism?(Select all that apply)
200 responses

The chart above represents the opinion of the respondents regarding what they would think is most beneficial pastoral counseling approach for trauma-responsive healing in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism. Majority of the respondents opted for individual counseling; expressive therapies and trauma focused cognitive behavioral approaches as the best approaches in ensuring quick healing process.

Chart VIII

In your opinion, what types of community support are essential for trauma responsive healing in affected communities?(Select all that apply)
200 responses

Chart VIII expressly shows the opinions of the respondents on the type of community support they consider to be essential for trauma healing in affected communities. With access to mental health professionals being the most accepted community support, financial assistance and reintegration programs were also highlighted in significant percentages.

Chart IX

Are there any existing community resources or initiatives in your area that provide support for trauma responsive healing?

200 responses

On the issue of existing community initiatives and resources, it was observed that in most affected communities of the respondents, there were no initiatives or resources to provide support for trauma responsive healing. From the findings, 93% of the entire respondents responded with a no to existing resources. However 7 % agreed that there were few resources and initiatives from government and NGOs.

Chart X

Do you have access to pastoral counseling services in your community?

199 responses

Chart X shows that 62.8 % of the total respondents in the study location do not have access to pastoral counseling; 31.2% claimed to have access but their services are not easily accessible, and 6% of the respondents agreed to have easy access to pastoral counseling. This needs to be addressed.

Chart XI

If pastoral counseling services were more accessible, would you be more likely to seek help for trauma-related issues?

199 responses

Chart XI shows that majority of the respondents would likely seek out help for trauma related issues if pastoral counseling were more accessible. The idea projected here is that accessibility is much keyed in enhancing trauma responsive healing for individual and even communities at large.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the provided charts offer valuable insights into the landscape of pastoral counseling and trauma-responsive healing in communities affected by terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria. Firstly, the demographic breakdown illustrates a higher response rate from females, indicating a potential gender disparity in engagement with trauma-related research or experiences. Additionally, the majority of respondents fell within the youthful age bracket of 18-25, highlighting the significant impact of terrorism on younger generations in the region. This demographic composition underscores the urgent need for tailored interventions to address the specific needs and vulnerabilities of youth affected by trauma.

Secondly, the data reveals several key perceptions and challenges regarding pastoral counseling and trauma-responsive healing. While a significant portion of respondents acknowledged familiarity with pastoral counseling approaches, a substantial proportion expressed uncertainty regarding their effectiveness in promoting trauma healing. Moreover, the lack of accessibility to pastoral counseling services emerged as a prominent issue, with a considerable majority reporting either no access or limited accessibility. However, there is a clear indication that improved accessibility to pastoral counseling could significantly enhance the likelihood of individuals seeking help for trauma-related issues, underscoring the critical role of accessibility in facilitating trauma-responsive healing within affected communities. These findings collectively emphasize the importance of addressing both awareness gaps and accessibility barriers to enhance the effectiveness of pastoral counseling interventions for trauma healing in Northeastern Nigeria.

Advancing Pastoral Counseling Principles for Trauma-Responsive Healing in Nigeria

Terrorism in Nigeria has caused significant trauma, especially in the northeast. To address these issues, trauma-responsive healing approaches, including pastoral counseling, are crucial. Christian-based counseling, rooted in Christian principles, offers emotional and spiritual

support, integrating faith-based perspectives into the healing process. This holistic approach to trauma recovery is essential for Nigeria's affected communities. Some of the basic Pastoral Counseling Principles for Trauma-Responsive Healing may include:

1. **Culturally Sensitive Approach:** Pastoral counselors need to be aware of and respect the cultural beliefs and practices of the affected communities. Understanding the specific religious and spiritual traditions of Nigerian Christianity is essential for effectively addressing trauma. This includes acknowledging the role of prayer, scripture, and communal support in the healing process.
2. **Creating Safe Spaces:** Trauma survivors require safe spaces where they can express their emotions, share their experiences and feel heard and understood. Pastoral counselors can establish safe environments within churches, community centers, or other gathering places, where individuals can openly discuss their trauma and receive support without judgment.
3. **Trauma-Informed Care:** Pastoral counselors should receive training in trauma-informed care to understand the impact of trauma on individuals' mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being. This knowledge enables counselors to provide appropriate support and interventions, considering the specific needs and vulnerabilities of trauma survivors.
4. **Collaborative Approach:** Collaboration between pastoral counselors and mental health professionals is crucial in addressing trauma in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism. By working together, these professionals can combine their expertise to provide a comprehensive and integrated approach to healing. This collaboration can involve referrals, joint training programs, and shared resources.

Conclusion

Owing to what we have observed, the terrorist issue in Nigerian communities has had far-reaching effects, including fatalities, evictions, economic disruption, and an atmosphere of dread, insecurity, and traumatic events. The injuries sustained go much beyond mere physical harm; they penetrate the core of the human psyche. Violence, loss, and displacement have all caused psychological and emotional traumas that have permanently altered the life of certain people, entire families, and entire communities. As a result, there is a need for pastoral care providers as well as professional counselors to intervene and offer hope to these afflicted victims. These care providers should make an effort to adopt a culturally sensitive approach, create safe spaces, implement trauma-informed care, and foster collaboration with mental health professionals when conducting counseling sessions.

Recommendations

This study therefore recommends that;

1. That collaborative approach which would involve community leaders, religious organizations and mental health professionals should be encouraged to foster innovative interventions and best practices in counseling communities affected by terrorism in Nigeria.

2. Access to Pastoral services must be made easy and accessible to trauma survivors in the affected Nigerian communities.
 3. Resources and initiatives should be mobilized and encouraged by both the pastoral caregivers and the government so as to pave way for sustainable trauma-responsive healing.
 4. Training and Capacity building must be taken into consideration. Professional development for pastoral caregivers in trauma-informed care must be encouraged and trauma-focused education must be integrated into theological institutions.
- Policy recommendations for supporting trauma survivors and affected communities should be issued by the Nigerian government at the three-tier levels.

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